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GAME INTERFACE DESIGN ACCORDING TO CHILDREN'S STAGE OF SPATIAL RECOGNITION DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to show through an investigative analysis that the appropriateness of commonly used horizontal scroll games intended for children of all ages depends on the developmental stages of spatial recognition. For this, the structural characteristics of the horizontal scrolling and spatial recognition theories were examined. Critical factors were selected through a focus group interview of experts. Three groups of children (aged 4-6, 7-8, and 9-11; 130 children total) were asked to play two games for 20 minutes each. Age differences in spatial recognition during play were analyzed. The results showed that there are stage-dependent recognition differences even after controlling for individual differences in spatial recognition. This finding, consistent with current spatial recognition theories, implies that horizontal scroll games are not necessarily appropriate for children of all ages. Therefore, game interface designs need to consider the spatial recognition stages of children.

Keywords: spatial recognition development of children, spatial recognition, horizontal game interface design

INTRODUCTION

Computer games are a new yet advanced form of play culture for children and affect their cognitive development. In the discussion of cognitive development of children and the utilization of cognitive abilities, computer games are deemed to be effective in improving hand-eye coordination (Ball,

1978, Lowery & Knirk, 1982, Orosy, 1989) and visual information processing abilities (Okagaki & Frensch, 1994). In addition, such games are also considered to be related to spatial recognition development (Armstrong 1993).

Currently, the industry has determined that almost all horizontal scroll games are appropriate for all ages. However, they actually do not offer a game interface that considers the spatial recognition development of children by stages. Even among the games available, there are only a few games for children's entertainment that are truly appropriate for their spatial recognition capacity. Some researchers have studied educational interfaces, such as touch-based games and web interfaces for children, but none have addressed the current, commercially available horizontal scroll game interfaces. This research focuses on commercialized horizontal scroll games for children's entertainment, not for education. This study focused on the characteristic factors of the game interfaces in "La Tale" and "Grand Chase." The study subjects were examined to determine how children in different age groups recognized the different characteristics of the game. A total of 130 children across differing age groups were asked to play one of the selected games for approximately 20 minutes. Therefore, this study aims to find out the characteristic, age-dependent differences in the processing of horizontal scroll game interfaces designed for children of all ages and what kind of differences in spatial recognition stages children display during game play.

The research hypotheses were as follows.

RESEARCH QUESTION 1

What are the characteristic factors of the horizontal scroll game interfaces designed for children of all ages?

RESEARCH QUESTION 2

Do the spatial recognition levels of children differ according to age?

RESEARCH QUESTION 3

What kind of differences in spatial recognition do children show?

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

SPATIAL RECOGNITION THEORIES

Spatial recognition is the ability to accurately understand relationships between spaces by recognizing directionality in one’s own body through movement and sensory cues within a space (Linn & Peterson, 1985). Behaviors within a space are established based on human recognition within spatial conditions, including shapes or colors, further informing the creation of that space. Therefore, spatial recognition is an understanding of the relationship between space and the human. Spatial recognition processes allow one to understand various specific and abstract objects and phenomena as specific visual shapes. Spatial recognition abilities therefore allow one to understand, transform, and express recognized relationships between objects and phenomena. Such capacities include the ability to recreate specific phenomena and objects from one’s location and position (Gardner, 1983; Amstrong, 1993). These principles are consistent with the work of Piaget who observed that spatial recognition changes over cognitive development with the characteristic shapes of the set stages and the recognized spaces within these stages highly variable. Piaget and Inhelder (1975) divided the spaces of spatial recognition development stages into shaped space, projected space, and geometric space. Piaget also saw spatial recognition abilities as a part of the general characteristics of logical growth. Spatial recognition abilities are thus an ability to discover and recognize a method in the initial direction of the observed path for the object and the

various locations. Piaget divided these abilities into a formal knowledge, that has the shape of the object, and a functional knowledge, that changes the shape, in the sensual functional period (ages 4-6; formal space). In a second division, proximity is the most important factor, with the characteristics of object differentiation, formed spatial recognition, selfish thoughts, and the inability to understand spatial relationships in the specific handling period (ages 7-8; projected space). Accordingly, when children in this stage enter school, an appropriate control of images and objects within a space occurs. This period still has limitations in specific situations and objects. In particular, it has the characteristics of transmitted and projected spatial control, an understanding of cross-sections and developmental figures, an initial acquisition of view-acceptance ability, and the inability to understand the theory of perspective drawing. Finally, in the formal controlling period with the lacking cubic effects of shadows (ages 9-11; Euclidean space), children can manage the formal rules that govern space and the concept of abstract space. In addition, they can realistically describe their understanding of shapes from visual perspective, analogically infer maps from the plane, describe rough sketches, and understand cubic spaces. Table 1 shows the detailed characteristics for spatial recognition by stages.

Stage	Spatial Recognition	Detailed Characteristics
Formal spatial manipulation Ages 4-6	Formal space	Proximity is the most important factor along with object differentiation, self-centered thoughts, recognition of formal spaces, and the inability to understand spatial relationships
Projected space manipulation Ages 7-8	Projected space	Can appropriately control the images and objects within a space. Limited to specific situations and objects. Transmitted and projected space manipulation.

Geometric spatial management Ages 9-11	Euclidean Space	Can handle the abstract regulations that govern the spaces and the abstract spaces and understands the changes of shapes depending on the view
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Table 1. Detailed characteristic of spatial recognition by stage

Roedder (1981) studied the pre-operation period, specific operation period, and the formal operation period for the controlling abilities of children. Roedder and Whitney (1992) further suggested developing the information amounts that are provided at different ratios according to the age that determines the amount of information usable.

HORIZONTAL SCROLL GAME INTERFACE

The role of the game interface triggers the relationship between the player and the game and also provides play-related information. Various communications with the players occur simultaneously. The visual information that overloads the sensory channels or that cannot be differentiated easily are related to the recognition abilities of the children (Liben, 1981). The horizontal scroll games provide set points and interfaces that game players, including children, can comfortably approach.

Figure 1. Horizontal scroll game play scene

The horizontal scroll method is one method of indicating progress from a side view in the gaming perspective. In the perspective categorization method, the operation screen, or dividing the play screen based on the importation status of the player, is not the standard graphic output. This method has the character move horizontally while the background moves from side to side. From the perspective of children with developing spatial

recognition abilities, horizontal scroll games have important implications. Unlike the progress methods of a full 3D, visual recognition skills require proper processing of the plane space. The interface system of a full 3D third-person perspective may overload children’s cognitive systems due to the rapid changes in perspectives for the children. (Baddeley,A 1993) Games with the horizontal scroll method show progress in the game using a side-to-side method while the map of the background moves. However, the changes of the character movements and the direction of the views are limited. The game space with the limited view acts as a factor that immerses young children in the game. The biggest characteristics of the horizontal scroll game are direct control through the simple use of a keyboard, more planes, and the layered depth in selecting the spatial senses between the backgrounds and the character relative to full 3D.

The game interface design starts from the layout of the screen (Rollings & Adams, 2004). What information is provided and where, as well as the method of maintaining overall game consistency, is determined by these layout decisions. How the areas on screen are used for these various purposes plays a big role in interactions.

Saunders & Novak (2007) showed that the game interface is divided into a manual interface and a visual interface, where the visual interface is generally related to the feedback as a place within the game interface. This spatial context includes the display and the perspective.

RESEARCH METHOD AND ANALYSIS

RESEARCH PROCEDURE AND SUBJECTS

The purpose of this study is to examine differences in spatial recognition abilities across differing age groups in the context of horizontal scroll game interfaces intended for children of all ages. Such research may suggest appropriate future directions in the horizontal scroll game interface design. The research methods and procedures are shown below.

Figure 2. Research model and procedures

This study first selected horizontal scroll games which are played with approximately equal frequency across differing ages and which can therefore be regarded as appropriate for all ages. Then, it investigated how children in different age groups recognize the characteristic factors of the game interfaces for "La Tale" and "Grand Chase." After extracting the characteristic factors of the space and the UI on screen through the focus group interview (FGI) of an expert group, the children were then interviewed on questions about locations and their understanding of the recognition factors arising during game play. With the permission of the parents, 130 children familiar with computers were allowed to play the games for 20 minutes. The characteristic factors that show the behaviors and recognition patterns during the play were specifically examined. And the space and the UI on the screen of the horizontal scroll game were divided according to the characteristic factors of the game, with the recognition patterns of factors in each type analyzed. The play of 130 total children was examined; 44 in the sensual functional period (ages 4-6); 43 children in the specific functional period (ages 7-8); and 43 children in formal functional period (ages 9-11). The subjects were limited to children who knew how to control computers. A basic explanation for the game manipulation was provided. The analysis was limited to the period after the game introduction screen and the server connection.

The games used in this study were "La Tale" and "Grand Chase" which are deemed appropriate for children of all ages. The platform was a PC. La Tale is a 2D MMO role playing game and is often played by younger children and was designed to have larger character movements and bigger characters for the women with lower "spatial recognition abilities" and younger children. The interface within the game is relatively direct, using the characteristics of MMORPG.

Figure 3. La Tale game screen

Figure 4. Grand Chase game screen

"Grand Chase" is an MO-action adventure game. It is somewhat challenging in the initial stages but has simpler information displays and high noteworthiness.

RESEARCH ANALYSIS

Horizontal Scroll Layer Structures and Characteristic Analysis

This study confirmed the results to carry out Research Question 1 through the processes described below. Through an FGI of the expert group with game experience of 4-5 years, the following characteristic spatial recognition factors for children with regards to horizontal scroll game interfaces were extracted.

- Differentiation between play stage and overall background
- Interaction between character movements and background
- Recognition of character status window and target window
- Recognition of character location
- Multitasking with playing and chatting
- Recognition of levels on screen UI

Figure 5 shows the pictorial explanation of the extracted factors.

Figure 5. The extracted factors

- Top left: status window
- Top middle: shortcut keys window
- Top right: mini map and navigation
- Center: character
- Bottom left: chatting window
- Background: gray screen - overall background
- Light brown path: background play stage

Characteristics of the Studied Interface Composition Factors

- **Background** - The map of the horizontal scroll game moves the map from side to side for the moving speed of the character and the map that intersects with the ground, water surface, and the space. There are direct backgrounds, which the character directly uses, and simple indirect backgrounds. Such backgrounds exist in layers. Whether these backgrounds will be expressed with perspective drawings will be determined.
- **Character** - The characters in the horizontal scrolls emphasize interaction with the background. Without changing the perspective or a separate navigation, the movement of the characters is the most important part of the horizontal scroll game.
- **Object or NPC** - Object, item, and NPC as well as the separation from the background.

- **Skills window, menu, chatting window, and navigation, status window** - For the spatial recognition aspects for children, the types and location of the visual information for the game space and the ability to understand one's location in the game background are important factors in the horizontal scroll game. Recognizing one's status is also important.

Components			Details
Name	La Tale	Grand Chase	
Status window	 Top left	Information on character's face, level, gauge of current state	
Chatting window	 Top left, below the status window	Communication with users and checking the information from the system message	
Shortcut key window		The commands in the game and frequently used icons	
Navigation and minimap		Current location and the NPC location	

Table 2. Basic components of research object

The standards for the interface components in the horizontal scroll games are the layers which are part of the system. Therefore, the spatial locations of the plane screen and the visual screen depth are shown below.

Figure 6. Layer order of the horizontal scroll game, spatial depth, and plane space of screen

This study selected the layer of the space that makes up the UI layout, namely the information and screen of the visual interface. The information transfer for

interactions, lists, levels, and icons are located on screen. The game background and the characters create the layer to take up the space with depth or in plane width on the screen.

Difference Analysis of the Spatial Recognition for Different Age Groups

According to the theories of Piaget, children develop recognition abilities as they grow through interactions with their surroundings over time. Therefore, the screen UI and the spatial recognition of the children in the horizontal scroll game were hypothesized to differ according to age.

Research Question 2: Do the spatial recognition levels of the children differ across ages in

Research Question 1?

Hypothesis 1: In the horizontal scroll games designed for children of all ages, the screen UI and the recognition ability within the context of the spatial interface will be different across different age groups.

To determine the confidence levels of this study, Cronbach's α value was measured. The overall α value from calculations for the six variants that were used in the measurements of the screen UI and the space interface recognition was 0.933. This is higher than the general standard of 0.7 for high internal consistency, thus indicating that the questions used here measured similar concepts.

Categorization	Cronbach's α
Items (N)	6
Alpha	0.933
Standardized items	0.933

Table 3. Confidence analysis

The game names in the following tables will be abbreviated as R for La Tale game and G for Grand Chase.

Recognition differences by age

The following ANOVAs were performed to analyze spatial recognition abilities by age,

Ⓐ Recognition differences for layer categories

In the layer categories of La Tale, the children aged 4-6 could not differentiate them (1.23). In contrast, those aged 7-8 could differentiate them (2.21) and those aged 9-11 could differentiate them accurately (2.93). The between-groups comparison yielded an F value of 175.151 ($p < 0.001$), a significant difference. In differentiating the layers in Grand Chase, children in the 4-6 age group could not differentiate them (1.23). Consistent with the preceding findings, however, those aged 7-8 could differentiate them (1.91) and those aged 9-11 could differentiate them accurately (2.77). The between-groups analysis produced an F value of 110.663 ($p < 0.001$), also a significant difference.

Category	Age 4-6 (n=44)	Age 7-8 (n=43)	Age 9-11 (n=43)	F value
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	
Layer differentiation R	1.23 (0.42)	2.21 (0.56)	2.93 (0.26)	175.151*
Layer differentiation G	1.23 (0.43)	1.91 (0.57)	2.77 (0.43)	110.663*

Table 4. Recognition differences in layer differentiation
* $p < 0.001$

The t-test to analyze the difference between layer differentiation recognition and layer differentiation recognition was not significant ($t = 1.376, p = 0.170$).

Category	Average	Standard deviation	t	p
Layer differentiation R	2.11	0.83	1.376	0.170
Layer differentiation G	1.97	0.79		

Table 5. Recognition differences in layer differentiation

Ⓑ Recognition differences in character movements

Regarding the character movements of La Tale, children aged 4-6 could not differentiate them (1.27), while those aged 7-8 could differentiate them (2.09) and children aged 9-11 could differentiate them accurately (2.67). For the analysis on the difference between the ages, the F value was 96.468 ($p < 0.001$), indicating a significant difference between the groups.

In the Grand Chase character movements, children aged 4-6 could not differentiate them (1.26), while those aged 7-8 could differentiate them to a certain extent (1.18) and children aged 9-11 could also differentiate them (2.40). The analysis between age groups showed an *F* value of 56.788 ($p < 0.001$), again indicating a significant difference.

Category	Ages 4-6 (n=44)			Ages 7-8 (n=43)			Ages 9-11 (n=43)			F value
	M	(SD)		M	(SD)		M	(SD)		
Character movements	R	1.27	(0.45)	2.09	(0.48)		2.67	(0.47)		96.468*
	G	1.26	(0.44)	1.81	(0.50)		2.40	(0.54)		56.788*

Table 6. Recognition differences in character movements
* $p < 0.001$

A t-test testing the differences in the recognition of the character movements in the games ($t = 2.113$, $p = 0.036$), indicated that character movement recognition differs significantly between the two games.

Category		Average	Standard deviation	t	p
Character movement	R	2.01	0.74	2.113	0.036
	G	1.82	0.68		

Table 7. Recognition differences in character movements in games

© Recognition differences in status window

Children aged 4-6 could not differentiate the status window of La Tale (1.16), while those aged 7-8 could somewhat differentiate the windows (1.51) and children aged 9-11 could differentiate them (2.49). A test of the age groups differences showed an *F* value of 90.511 ($p < 0.001$) indicating a significant group difference.

In the status window of Grand Chase, children aged 4-6 could not differentiate them (1.16), children aged 7-8 could differentiate them to some degree (1.51), and the children aged 9-11 could differentiate them (2.49). The differences in age groups yielded an *F* value of 87.162 ($p < 0.001$), signifying a significant difference.

Category	Ages 4-6 (n=44)			Ages 7-8 (n=43)			Ages 9-11 (n=43)			F value
	M	(SD)		M	(SD)		M	(SD)		
Recognition of status window	R	1.16	(0.37)	1.51	(0.55)		2.49	(0.51)		90.511*
	G	1.16	(0.37)	1.51	(0.55)		2.49	(0.51)		87.162*

Table 8. Recognition differences in status windows
* $p < 0.001$

The t-test analyzing the difference between the games for status window recognition ($t = -0.120$, $p = 0.905$) indicated no significant difference.

Category		Average	Standard deviation	t	p
Recognition of status window	R	1.71	0.74	-0.120	0.905
	G	1.72	0.74		

Table 9. Recognition differences of status window for each game

© Recognition differences of chatting window

For the chatting window of La Tale, children aged 4-6 (1.07) and 7-8 (1.21) could not differentiate them, although those aged 9-11 (2.53) could. The analysis of age differences produced an *F* value of 176.791, ($p < 0.001$), a significant difference. In the Grand Chase chatting window, children aged 4-6 (1.07) and ages 7-8 (1.30) could not differentiate them while children aged 9-11 (2.53) could, consistent with the findings for La Tale. Tests of these differences yielded an *F* value 148.905 ($p < 0.001$), again indicating a significant difference.

Category	Ages 4-6 (n=44)			Ages 7-8 (n=43)			Ages 9-11 (n=43)			F value
	M	(SD)		M	(SD)		M	(SD)		
Chatting window recognition	R	1.07	(0.26)	1.21	(0.41)		2.53	(0.51)		176.791*
	G	1.07	(0.26)	1.30	(0.47)		2.53	(0.51)		148.905*

Table 10. Recognition differences in chatting window
* $p < 0.001$

The t-test analyzing the difference between the games for chatting window recognition ($t = -0.421$, $p = 0.674$) showed no significant difference.

Category		Average	Standard deviation	t	p
Recognition of chatting window	R	1.60	0.77	-0.421	0.674
	G	1.64	0.77		

Table 11. Recognition differences for game chatting window

© Recognition differences for indicated values

For the indicated values of La Tale, children aged 4-6 (1.05) and 7-8 (1.02) could not differentiate them although children aged 9-11 (2.42) could. Tests of these age differences showed an *F* value of 265.432 ($p < 0.001$), a significant difference.

In the indicated values of Grand Chase, children aged 4-6 (1.05) and 7-8 (1.02) could not differentiate them while children aged 9-11 could (2.42). The age differences analysis yielded an *F* value of 259.098 ($p < 0.001$), a significant difference.

Category		Ages 4-6 (n=44)	Ages 7-8 (n=43)	Ages 9-11 (n=43)	F value
		M(SD)	M(SD)	M(SD)	
Recognition of values	R	1.05 (0.21)	1.02 (0.15)	2.42 (0.50)	265.432*
	G	1.05 (0.21)	1.02 (0.15)	2.42 (0.50)	259.098*

Table 12. Recognition differences for indicated values
* $p < 0.001$

The t-test analyzing the difference in the value recognition in each game ($t = -0.084, p = 0.933$) was not significant.

Category		Average	Standard deviation	t	p
Recognition of values	R	1.49	0.73	-0.084	0.933
	G	1.50	0.73		

Table 13. Recognition differences between indicated values of the game

① Recognition differences for one’s own location information

In the indicated values of La Tale, children aged 4-6 (1.05) and 7-8 (1.05) could not differentiate them while children aged 9-11 (2.35) could. Tests of the

differences between age groups showed an *F* value of 231.168 ($p < 0.001$), a significant difference.

In the indicated values of Grand Chase, children aged 4-6 (1.05) and 7-8 (1.02) could not differentiate them while children aged 9-11 (2.35) could. The analysis of these age differences showed an *F* value of 225.534 ($p < 0.001$) which is significantly different.

Category		Ages 4-6 (n=44)	Ages 7-8 (n=43)	Ages 9-11 (n=43)	F value
		M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	
Location information	R	1.05(0.21)	1.05(0.21)	2.35(0.48)	231.168*
	G	1.05(0.21)	1.02(0.21)	2.35(0.48)	225.534*

Table 14. Recognition differences on location information
* $p < 0.001$

A t-test found that location information recognition does not differ significantly between the games ($t = -0.085, p = 0.932$).

Category		Average	SD	t	p
Location information	R	1.47	0.69	-0.085	0.932
	G	1.48	0.70		

Table 15. Recognition differences for location information per game

Recognition differences by age groups and recognition characteristics analysis

The behavioral analysis results for Research Question 3 incorporated a selection of 130 children who could manipulate computers within two different horizontal scroll games. Those children in the formal functional period children (ages 9-11) used the background, character status, character object menus, and even multiple chatting windows to sensitively respond to character movement changes. Where the background was windy, they moved between the spaces freely by jumping and accurately attacking to show that they were clearly recognizing the status of the other objects as well. They also used the navigation (map) function with free movements and showed clearly where one was located. Children in the specific functional period (ages 7-8) lacked the ability to recognize the menu

information and could not differentiate the background and the menu accurately, although they did recognize them to a certain extent. The children in this period were interested in the interactions between the character and the direct background and moved continuously with repetitive keyboard presses but with lower responses to reading the letters in the chatting window and the value changes. They also had lower language recognition and focused more on the character's movements, rather than the chatting window. Furthermore, they interacted more with the visual and auditory aspects when choosing icons. Children in the sensual functional period (ages 4-6) took more time in recognizing the overall movement of the game. The children in this period lack the ability to differentiate spaces and cannot differentiate the perspective background and the play stage. This limited their character's movements horizontally with children only rarely using the attacks and right or left jumps accurately. The characters also often fell while moving between the spaces. They also could not differentiate the spaces between the indirect backgrounds and the play stage, causing the character's location to circle around in place. This phenomenon arises from the lack of spatial recognition and the inability to recognize them in detail. Roedder (1992) stated that children only recognize structure by intuitively recognizing the whole for the recognized object. The screen UI and the space interface of the horizontal scroll games designed for children of all ages requires that the game interfaces be recognizable by particularly young players. The game interfaces that young children can recognize should clearly distinguish between characters and backgrounds, including a clear separation of colors and shapes. According to the present findings, La Tale showed a higher recognition level in the interaction between character movements and background than Grand Chase.

CONCLUSION

This study aimed to consider game interface design with a particular focus on children's spatial recognition in horizontal scroll games designed for children of all ages. To this end, the present effort extracted the structural characteristics and factors

of horizontal scrolls through an expert group FGI to use such factors. Age difference in each stage were significant. In particular, children in the shaped spatial manipulation period (ages 4-6), exhibited characteristics such as incongruent recognition and the inability to understand object volumes or areas in the whole context. This period represents the early formation of spatial concepts and the ability to recognize shaped spaces although the understanding of spatial relationships is still premature. The concept of horizontal and vertical in particular is still not developed. These children are therefore unable to jump and move horizontally at the same time. Children in the projected space manipulation period (ages 7-8) can recognize the entities visually. In addition, they also understand the concept of boundaries and can differentiate where the game's spatial boundaries lie, although the differentiation was not always entirely clear. Finally, children in the geometric space manipulation period (ages 9-11), are able to accurately differentiate visual shapes and differentiate the screen UI during game play. They can recognize spatial concepts and layers as well as easily recognize one's location and the other person's location. Therefore, these two game interfaces, intended for users of all ages, need to better integrate and organize horizontal scroll game interfaces in order to better adapt to the spatial recognition abilities of younger children; even when younger children can handle computers, the current interfaces still make recognition of key game elements more difficult. This study only focused on spatial recognition, but focusing also on the content transfer of colors, shapes, and other information for these age groups will further allow children across differing ages to play computer games more appropriately.

In considering these conclusions, it is nonetheless important to note that the present study is not necessarily broadly generalizable because it did not theorize across a broader sampling of children. Recognition development changes depend in part on the environment and must therefore be tested with children from different areas with completely different environments and with a broader range of individual differences. Despite these limits, this study showed that behaviors in each game interface differed according to the characteristics of the

spatial recognition development stage of each age group. If horizontal scroll games can organize game interfaces with regard to spatial recognition development to suit the layer standards, then the children can optimally interact with the game interface.

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